

SOLVED AND UNSOLVED PROBLEMS OF COORDINATION TRAINING IN SPORT

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Introduction

The issue of coordination training in sport has a further development at present (Lyakh, 1983-2009; Lyakh & Sadowski, 1999; Neumaier, Mechling, 1995; Starosta, 2003, 2006; Simonek, 2006; Neumaier, 2003; Neumaier, Mechling, Straus, 2002; Hirtz, 1995, 2007, Roth, 1998; Sadowski, 2000; Raczek, 1991, 1999, 2000; Raczek, Mynarski, Lyakh, 2003 and others).

However, as yet, there are no generally works whose authors would evaluate what has been done in this field, and what to improve in the future.

The analysis of references in the literature provides the methods of experts' evaluations, surveys, questionnaires, laboratories, computer and motor tests for evaluation of CMAs (Coordination Motor Abilities), technical skills and other characteristics, pedagogical experiment, methods of mathematical statistics. The subjects of this study were the athletes of playing sports events: basketball players, volleyball players, handball players and footballers, athletes involved in single combats (Greco-Roman and free-style wrestling, kickboxing, tae kwon do), acrobats of different age, sex, period of sports experience and skill level. The author of this paper was a tutor of more than 10 dissertations in this field.

In this paper we discuss main aspects of coordination training in sport.

Results & Discussion

1. The objective and place of coordination preparation in the system of long-term training is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Objective of coordination preparation in sports games and single combats (Lyakh, 1995).

2. Cas (Coordination Abilities) training should be outlined and organized as an independent part of training and performed for 15-45 minutes. The intervals between these types of training should be the same as during "strength" and "endurance" training.
3. Training of sports specific CAs results in their increase only when the selected physical exercises reflect typical competitive conditions.
4. The sequence in CAs training. It is well-known that success, especially in sport games and single combats, depends on many CAs. From practical point of view, one should answer the question - which ability should start the training process in order to provide the basis for other CAs, and what sequence should be used?
5. The physical exercises used for CAs training should be thought and executed correctly from technical point of view. This is particularly important while training of CAs in children and youth.
6. The duration of loads and rest intervals during performance of coordination exercises depends on the level of athlete's technical skills, conditioning and tactical preparation, actual CA which improves due to given exercise, way of conjugated development of coordination and conditioning abilities as well as upon the number of players participating in exercise, their degree of resistance, number of balls and other factors.
7. The essential provision of coordination training - systematic usage of special coordination exercises aimed at development of the most significant for the given sports event CAs (See Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. The general coaches' opinions (n = 115) on the significance of particular CAs in basketball training (Glasauer, Nieber, 1999).

8. One of the major methodical problems of coordination training consists of optimum combination (conjugated impact) of coordination exercises aimed at CAs development with those influencing various conditioning and complex abilities (speed, strength, endurance, flexibility and their combinations). As a matter of fact, scientists and coaches have to develop such exercises.

9. From the point of view of CAs training strategy, especially with regard to children and youth, it is very important to know sensitive (the most favorable) periods of development of these abilities as well as age and individual peculiarities of their formation (See Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. The age when children reach 25, 50, 75, 100% of total development of CAs (Lyakh, 1990).

10. One of the most important theoretic-methodical provisions of CAs training is their development with account for lateralization (Starosta, 1990, 2003, 2006; Lyakh, Sadowski, 1999, etc.).

Conclusion

The paper deals with theoretic-methodological and methodical provisions of CAs training of athlete in the system of long-term preparation. The individual aspects of further scientific studies and objectives confronting sports practice are indicated. The efficiency of coordination training in sport was supported by the results of experimental studies of the author and his students carried out on basketball players (Lyakh, Mikolajec, Zajac, 1998; Mikolajec, Lyakh, 1998; Lyakh, 2003), handball players (Pawelak, 2003; Bodasinski, 2009), football players (men and women) (Witkowski 2003; Lyakh, Witkowski, Zmuda, 2003; Lyakh, Witkowski, 2004, 2009; Lyakh et.al. 2005; Lipecki, 2009), volleyball players (Grzadziel, Lyakh, 2000; Frączek, 2009) and kick boxers, tae kwon do (Sadowski, 2000), single combats (Greco-Roman and free-style wrestling) (Gierczuk, 2004) acrobats of various qualifications (Sarsiekiew, 2009).

However, there is a need to investigate further studies after establishing the efficiency of all variants of coordination training during long-term preparation system of an athlete mainly with the application of special co-ordinational devices (stands) and using the exercises of increased co-ordinational complexity.

Keywords: sport, coordination, coordination training, coordination abilities.